

GEO MORPHOMETRY
PERUGIA ITALY

2025
JUNE 9-13

Global Assessment of Mining Activities Using TanDEM-X Digital Elevation Change Maps

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Abstract—The growing global demand for raw materials has led to a significant expansion in mineral extraction, resulting in widespread social and environmental impacts. However, the world's mining areas and the volumes of extracted and deposited materials remain poorly documented, limiting our ability to assess their full impact and implement effective mitigation measures to reduce environmental and social damage. To address these challenges, we use global remote sensing products to estimate the volumes of excavated and deposited materials from opencast mining activities worldwide. Using the recently produced TanDEM-X 30m Change Maps, which provide global elevation change information, and the global-scale mining polygons dataset designating mining areas, we assess the contribution of each continent and country to the volume of excavated and deposited material. Our results show that, globally, the total volume of material excavated between the periods of 2011–2015 and 2016–2022 was 180,989 million cubic meters, while the volume of deposited material was 186,347 million cubic meters. During this period, the depth of the mines (and height of heaps) has increased on average by approximately 2–5 meters per square meter, depending on the continent. In North America, for example, the total excavated volume was equivalent to digging a hole of roughly 10x10x10 meters in size per every square kilometer of the continent, while in Australia, such a hole would be more than twice the size. The majority of opencast mining occurred in China, Indonesia, Australia, Russia, and the U.S. However, when normalized by country area, the data revealed a higher intensity of mining activities in smaller countries such as Suriname and Czechia. The calculated volumes of excavated and deposited material provide a more accurate representation of mining intensity than site area alone and enable cross-site comparisons for global monitoring.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the growing global demand for raw materials has fueled a significant expansion of mineral extraction, leading to a wide range of social and environmental consequences worldwide. However, despite the sector's global importance, the impacts of the world's mining areas remain poorly documented [1]. This knowledge gap is particularly concerning given the growing push for digitalization and the sector's rapid transformation, driven by the increasing demand for critical materials such as cobalt and lithium while reducing our reliance on fossil fuels [2].

To address these challenges and bridge the knowledge gap, remote sensing data are increasingly being utilized as a valuable resource for mapping mining areas. For instance, Maus et al. [3] used satellite imagery to develop a global dataset representing the extent of land used for mining. This and other existing datasets, such as the S&P Global Market Intelligence database, typically represent mines as points or polygons and lack complete and site-specific information on mining intensity, including the volumes of extracted and disposed materials, which neglects the differences in the scale of impacts among mining locations [1].

Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) of Difference (DoD) are remote sensing products that can be useful in detecting and quantifying changes in surface elevation over time. By comparing elevation data from different time periods, DoD allows researchers to monitor various earth surface processes, including anthropogenic activities such as mining. In 2023, the German Aerospace Center released the TanDEM-X DEM Change Maps, representing global surface elevation changes yielded by

comparing the first global TanDEM-X DEM (acquired between 2011 and 2015) with the newly acquired DEM scenes (2016 to 2022) [4]. This dataset offers an excellent resource for assessing volumes of extracted and disposed materials in opencast mines.

This study aimed to estimate the volumes of excavated and deposited materials resulting from opencast mining activities worldwide and the differences among continents and countries in this respect.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The presented study used two global datasets: The TanDEM-X 30m Change Maps [4], which provide global elevation change information, and the global-scale mining polygons dataset (version 1), which represents mining areas [3].

TanDEM-X satellite mission is a joint effort by the German Aerospace Center and Airbus Defence and Space to map the Earth's surface. It is a constellation of two satellites, flying in close orbit formation and acquiring radar images of the Earth surface [5]. The data acquired during the mission were used for the development of several global digital elevation models. The TanDEM-X 30m DEM Change Maps at a 1 arc-second spatial resolution represent the most recent addition to the family of the mission products. TanDEM-X 30m DEM Change Maps are available in two versions [4] [6]. Here, we used the last DEM change, which represents elevation changes between the TanDEM-X 30m Edited DEM – produced using data acquired over a four-year period between December 2010 and January 2015 – and most recent data acquired between 2016 and 2022 (hereafter DCM). DCM is available from <https://geoservice.dlr.de/web/maps/tdm:dcm30>.

The Global-scale mining polygons dataset (version 1) consists of 21,060 polygons covering 57,277 km² of mining areas. Mining areas were identified using coordinates from the S&P Global Market Intelligence database and manually delineated through visual inspection of several satellite-based, cloudless images (Google Satellite, Microsoft Bing Imagery, and Sentinel-2). The polygons cover various land uses related to mining activities such as open cuts, waste dumps, and processing facilities but they do not distinguish between them [3]. This dataset provides comprehensive information on global mining, though it is still far from covering all existing mines worldwide [1]. The reported omission and commission errors of mines were 21% and 3%, respectively [3]. The global-scale mining polygons dataset (v1) is available from <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910894>.

We assessed the volume of excavated and deposited material (i.e., the overall volumetric terrain change) for all mining polygons worldwide. To calculate the volumetric change, we summed up the elevation differences of all cells in the DCM within each mining polygon and multiplied the result by the area of a single cell. To differentiate between positive and negative elevation changes (i.e., to distinguish between mining and dumping areas), we treated

cells with positive and negative values in the DCM separately. This approach provided three values for each mining polygon: the volume of excavated material, the volume of deposited material, and the overall volumetric change (i.e., the sum of excavated and deposited material). Subsequently, we calculated the contribution of individual countries and continents to global mining activities and their associated volumetric changes.

III. RESULTS

Worldwide, the total volume of excavated material during the period 2011–2015 and 2016–2022 was 180,989 million m³ while the volume of deposited material was 186,347 million m³. Figure 1 illustrates the contribution of each continent to the volume of deposited and excavated material.

Figure 1. Contribution of each continent to the total volume of deposited and excavated material from opencast mining activities.

During the studied period, the depth of the mines (and the height of the heaps) has increased on average by approximately 2-

5 meters per square meter of mining areas, depending on the continent. Figure 2 compares the excavated (negative values) and deposited (positive values) material across each continent relative to the area of mining sites and the continent's total area. For example, in North America, the total excavated volume was equivalent to digging a hole of approximately 10x10x10 meters in size per square kilometer (Fig. 2).

A summary of the total volume of deposited and excavated material classified by country showed that the majority of opencast mining activities were concentrated in five countries: China, Indonesia, Australia, Russian Federation, and the United States (Fig. 3). This ranking slightly differed from the ranking based solely on the area of mining sites (Fig. 4). When normalized by a country area, however, the data revealed a higher intensity of mining activities in smaller countries such as Suriname, New Caledonia, Germany, and Czechia (Fig. 3). Only Indonesia was included among the top 5 countries according to both above-mentioned assessment criteria.

Figure 2. Comparison of excavated material (negative values) and deposited material (positive values) across each continent, shown relative to the area of mining sites (top) and the continent's total area (bottom)

Figure 3. Ranking of countries according to the total volumes of deposited and excavated material (top) and according to the volumes relative to each country's area (bottom).

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

We demonstrated the usability of TanDEM-X 30m Change Maps for analyzing global mining activities. The calculated volumes of excavated and deposited material provide a quantitative indicator of mining intensity and its impact on Earth's surface topography. The calculated volumes account for differences in the magnitude of impacts between mining sites and provide a more accurate representation of the effects of mining activities on the surrounding areas compared to the simple use of mining site area [1]. The volumes of excavated and deposited material offer a standardized way to evaluate mining impacts globally and enable cross-site and cross-country comparisons of mining activities, providing a tool for global monitoring and enhancing transparency in the mining sector. Moreover, the volumes can aid in assessing the long-term risks of mining activities to local ecosystems and communities, facilitating early intervention strategies for mitigating damage.

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Figure 4. Ranking of countries by mining area and volume. In this case, the volume is calculated as the sum of the excavated and deposited materials.

The results of this exploratory analysis show terrain changes caused by mining activities over a relatively short period. Future studies should, therefore, incorporate near-global topographic data from the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM), acquired in 2000, to provide a more comprehensive assessment of mining activities in this century. Additionally, a newer version of the Global-scale mining polygons dataset is available now, including 44,929 polygon features covering 101,583 km² [7].

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was funded by the Horizon Europe project EarthBridge (grant agreement No. 101079310). Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.